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The Role of Historical Elements in Explaining the Principle of Imamate

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Abstract

The presentation and elucidation of profound Shi'a teachings, deeply rooted in scripture and tradition, necessitate a conducive environment. The realisation of such an environment is inextricably linked to the alignment or misalignment of influential historical elements, namely the political, social, cultural, and economic components. To accurately analyse phenomena within their historical context, it is imperative to recognise and utilise the historical elements that have shaped those events. The term "historical element" refers to any incident or minor component within the broader social, cultural, political, and occasionally economic framework that has played a role in shaping a particular intellectual current throughout history. Without considering the entirety of these components and their degree of alignment or misalignment, disregarding the influence of the unseen and divine realm in comprehending religious content, the analysis of any phenomenon remains incomplete. A thoughtful examination of these elements underscores their impact on the process of presenting the Shi'a epistemological framework, both in summary and in detail, during various periods of imamate presence without altering its fundamental principles. This study endeavours to explore three primary discussions: first, the theoretical and Quranic foundations and the question of why a summary and detailed explanation are necessary; second, outlining how historical elements play a role; and third, presenting comparative examples within the summary and detailed framework. The second section aims to elucidate these aspects, thereby enabling a comparative discussion of the explanation of epistemological teachings.

Keywords: Shi'a teachings, scripture and tradition, conducive environment, historical context, political elements

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Background

Historical Elements

To conduct a genuine analysis of a phenomenon, it is essential to identify and utilise the historical elements that have influenced that event. Therefore, the term "historical element" refers to any incident or minor component within the broader social, cultural, political, and occasionally economic framework that has played a role in shaping a particular intellectual current throughout history. Without considering the entirety of these components and their degree of alignment or misalignment, disregarding the influence of the unseen and divine realm in comprehending religious content, the analysis of any phenomenon remains incomplete.

1. Types of historical elements

1.1. Political Factors

In a general sense, politics involves the pursuit, maintenance, expansion, or demonstration of authority and power and its utilisation to advance specific goals within a society. Consequently, any effort by rulers to maintain the stability of their regime in various dimensions, and activities by opponents of the regime aimed at confronting and weakening it, are considered political factors. Therefore, our understanding of political factors encompasses any action or reaction undertaken with consideration of the institution of authority and power in pursuit of specific objectives. Examples of these factors include:

1.1.1. Political Atmosphere (Repression)

The suppression of intellectual freedom leads to societal stagnation, hindering progress and preventing access to knowledge that plays a crucial role in shaping political, cultural, and social landscapes. For nearly two centuries during the lifetime of the Ahl al-Bayt (peace be upon them), the Umayyad and Abbasid rulers successfully implemented a repressive atmosphere to maintain power and restrict access to such knowledge. A review of the reigns of rulers like Muawiyah, Yazid, Ibn Ziyad, Hajjaj, Mansur, Mutawakkil, Hisham, and others reveals the severity of this repression.

The martyrdom of Imams and numerous companions, and the exile or imprisonment of followers, exemplify this repressive environment. Additionally, Muawiyah's directives to his provincial governors, instructing them to treat Shi'ites with the utmost severity, cut off their stipends from the public treasury, and subject anyone expressing affection for Ali ibn Abi Talib (peace be upon him) to torture and harassment, further illustrate the aforementioned political atmosphere.

Beyond the oppressive era of Muawiyah and his harsh treatment of Muslims, such as the martyrdom of Hujr ibn Adi and his companions, as well as the incident of Hadramiyin, a clear example of repression can be seen during the reign of Hajjaj ibn Yusuf. He surpassed other tyrants in his hostility towards the Prophet (peace be upon him and his progeny) and his insults towards him. Hajjaj did not hesitate to shed blood and commit unprecedented atrocities. The extent of his brutal killings, excluding those on battlefields, is estimated to be as high as one hundred and twenty thousand people.

The repressive atmosphere during the reign of Mansur al-Abbasi was so intense that despite the widespread curiosity among Shi'ites to identify Imam Kazim (peace be upon him), the Imam exercised the utmost caution in revealing his identity. He instructed his followers: "Whoever among you recognises him, informs him and obtains his pledge of secrecy. If you disclose it, it will lead to slaughter," then the Imam pointed to his throat. These instances demonstrate how the Imams managed to disseminate their teachings under such political repression.

1.1.2. Governmental Responsibilities:

Holding governmental positions and utilising them, either by aligning governance with the dissemination of knowledge or not, can facilitate the spread of teachings. Clear examples of this occurred during the time of Imam Ali (peace be upon him) and the Imamate of Imam Reza (peace be upon him).

Imam Ali's extensive efforts in propagating the Prophet's teachings, including theological sermons, compiling hadiths, and educating disciples, clearly illustrate this point. Furthermore, Ma'mun's statement regarding Imam Reza's Imamate highlights the Imam's astute use of his position:

"Now that we have taken this course (Imamate) with him and erred in his matter, placing ourselves on the edge of a precipice by elevating him..."

Historically, this statement was made after the Imam's migration to Marv, where Imam Reza, utilising his political power and drawing people's attention towards himself, presented the most extensive argument and explanation on the topic of Imamate.

1.1.3. Movements and Uprisings Against the Government:

When an influential movement or political uprising occurs in society, it naturally triggers reactions among supporters, opponents, and those seeking answers. Consequently, opportunities for expression and dissemination of teachings arise. Examples of such movements and uprisings include Lady Fatima's sermon and Imam Ali's refusal to pledge allegiance; the uprising of Imam Hussain (peace be upon him); Zayd ibn Ali; and the uprising of Hussain ibn Ali, known as Sahib Fakh. For instance, the uprising and martyrdom of Imam Hussain (peace be upon him) against Yazid's rule led to increased awareness in society regarding the corruption of the government and other issues. The Imam, explaining the reason for his uprising, stated:

"I have not come out of Medina for rebellion, transgression, corruption, or oppression. Rather, I have come out to seek peace and reconciliation among my grandfather's nation. I intend to enjoin good and forbid evil, and to act according to the tradition of my grandfather."

In another example, when news of the martyrdom of Hussain ibn Ali, known as Sahib Fakh, reached Imam Kazim (peace be upon him), he said:

"By God, he departed and was martyred while being a righteous Muslim, fasting, enjoining good, and forbidding evil. There is no one like him in his family."

1.1.4. Political Propaganda

Undoubtedly, any government, institution, or even individual can utilise political manoeuvring and propaganda to foster public attraction or repulsion and even extend beyond that. For instance, during the Battle of Siffin, a young man from Muawiyah's army, influenced by such propaganda, addressed the companions of Amir al-Mu'minin (Imam Ali) about his reason for participating in the war:

"I fight you because I have been told that your master does not pray, and neither do you. I also fight you because your companion killed our Caliph, and you aided him in the killing." [13]

Similarly, Imam Sajjad (peace be upon him) recounts a conversation with Marwan ibn al-Hakam regarding the defamation of Imam Ali (peace be upon him):

"Marwan ibn al-Hakam told me that there was no one among the people who defended our master (Uthman) like your master (Ali). I asked, then why do you speak ill of him

from the pulpits? " He replied, " The government cannot be sustained except through this method." [14]

Furthermore, Abdullah ibn Ubaydullah explains the reason for defaming Imam Ali (peace be upon him):

"If the people knew what we knew about the virtues of Ali, they would disperse from us and turn to the children of Ali." [15]

These instances demonstrate the effectiveness of malicious propaganda in shaping the political atmosphere of society.

In another example, Muawiyah's propaganda machine, by subtly suggesting that Imam Hassan (peace be upon him) was plotting to overthrow the government, turned the situation against the Imam. This is evident in the words of Abd al-Rahman ibn Jabir al-Hadrami, a resident of Hims (near Damascus), who said:

"My father rebuked Hassan and said, 'People say you intend to seek the Caliphate.' Hassan replied, 'If the skulls of the Arabs were in my hands, they would be willing to make peace with whomever I make peace with and fight whomever I fight. But I have abandoned it for the pleasure of God. Do I now seek to attain it with the help of the people of Hijaz?'" [16]

In yet another instance, Yahya ibn Khalid al-Barmaki attempted to weaken the Shi'a's faith through a propaganda ploy. After Imam Kazim (peace be upon him) was imprisoned, Yahya addressed Salim (a Muslim), the head of the House of Wisdom, saying:

"I have nullified the religion of the Rafidis (Shiites) because they believe that religion cannot endure without a living Imam. Now they do not know whether their Imam is alive or dead." [17]

These examples clearly illustrate the impact of government propaganda in isolating the Imam from the progress of knowledge.

It is important to note that some narrations indicate that the Imams (peace be upon them) were not obligated to answer the questions of their companions. In some narrations, the reason is attributed to the repressive political atmosphere. For instance, when Muhammad ibn Abi Nasr inquired about a matter from Imam Reza (peace be upon him), the Imam initially refrained from answering and then said:

"If we were to tell you everything you want, it would bring harm upon you and lead to the capture of the guardian of this affair... You witness the actions of these pharaohs in Iraq." [18]

1.2. Cultural Factors

Culture, as the collective reservoir of knowledge, beliefs, customs, and values that imbue human life with meaning and direction, operates on both individual and societal levels. It encompasses knowledge, science, traditions, and various inclinations. In this context, cultural factors are those that contribute to shaping this meaning and direction. From this perspective, the public's receptiveness to teachings, the presence of intellectuals, a spirit of inquiry and pursuit of knowledge, and engagement with new ideas can be considered cultural factors that play a role in this directional influence. The following are the most significant of these factors:

1.2.1. Embrace of Teachings

A society's emphasis on knowledge and the exploration of the unknown fosters a spirit of inquiry and expands the boundaries of understanding.

A comparison between the cultural conditions during the period of hadith writing prohibition and the era preceding it reveals a growing public interest in knowledge. A narration from Imam Sajjad (peace be upon him) states:

"We do not know what to do with the people. If we tell them some of the things we have heard from the Prophet (peace be upon him and his progeny), they ridicule it, and if we do not tell them, it is difficult for us to bear." [19]

However, during the time of Imam Baqir (peace be upon him), the general inclination towards acquiring knowledge shifted due to the emergence of certain factors, the effects of which became apparent during the era of Imam Jafar al-Sadiq (peace be upon him). Imam al-Sadiq describes the nuances of this shift as follows:

"Before Abu Ja'far (Imam Baqir), the Shi'a did not even know their Hajj rituals or what was lawful and unlawful... until their situation reached a point where the people became dependent on them, after they had been dependent on the people." [20]

1.2.2. Presence of Intellectuals

In every era of the Ahl al-Bayt (peace be upon them) lives, where a gathering of intellectuals was abundant, the profound explanation of teachings, along with their details, occurred with greater intensity. During the time of the two Sadiq's (Imams Baqir and Jafar al-Sadiq), examples of this intellectual gathering can be observed. The Imams praised these people for their extensive knowledge and significant contributions to the growth of knowledge. For instance, Imam Baqir (peace be upon him) addressed Aban ibn Taghlib, saying:

"Sit in the mosque of Medina and issue fatwas for the people; indeed, I would like to see someone like you among the Shi'a." [21]

Another example relates to the four scholarly companions of Imam Jafar al-Sadiq (peace be upon him). While the permissiveness of the Ghulat movement intensified in opposition to the companions of the Prophet (peace be upon him), the Imam endeavoured to safeguard the Shi'a community from harm by referring them to these four individuals.

A narration from Jamil ibn Darraj in the book "Ikhtiyar Ma'rifat al-Rijal" emphasises the influence of this intellectual group. [22]

1.2.3. Spirit of Inquiry and Pursuit of Knowledge

In addition to what has been mentioned, the inquisitiveness of some companions of the Imams (peace be upon them) led to their profound knowledge and the dissemination and elaboration of teachings. A careful examination of their narrations indicates that whenever the number of inquisitive individuals increased, the details of the subjects also expanded. The era of the two Sadiq's (peace be upon them) can be considered the first period of the presence of such individuals. Figures like Jabir ibn Yazid al-Jufi, Zurara ibn A'yan, Burayd ibn Muawiyah, Abu Basir al-Asadi, Muhammad ibn Muslim, Hamran ibn A'yan, Hisham ibn Salim, Hisham ibn Hakam, Mu'mina al-Taq, and others are examples of such individuals. Muhammad ibn Muslim, who studied under Imam Baqir and Imam al-Sadiq (peace be upon them) for many years, said:

"I asked Abu Ja'far (Imam Baqir) about everything that I had doubts about. I asked him thirty thousand hadiths, and Abu Abdullah (Imam al-Sadiq) sixteen thousand hadiths." [23]

In another instance, Hisham ibn Hakam, when faced with a question from Ibn Abi al-Awja that he could not answer, travelled to Medina to seek the answer from the Imam. [24] He also said about his inquiries from the Imam:

"In the land of Mina, I asked Imam al-Sadiq about five hundred theological issues." [25]

In an effort to get clarification on his doubts and worries, Hamran ibn A'yan asked the Imam about a statement by Zurara and its critique. [26]

This is in contrast to earlier times when examples of such a spirit of inquiry were absent in response to Imam Ali's (peace be upon him) famous statement: "Ask me before you lose me." [27]

1.2.4. Encounter with New Ideas (Translation Movement)

Among the influential factors in the translation of Persian, Greek, and Roman texts into Arabic, which began around the mid-Umayyad period, were the cultural proximity and social-cultural freedoms of various Christian groups with Muslims, as well as the influence of the Christian community in the court of Muawiyah and other Umayyad caliphs as scribes in the administrative system. [28] This movement, in addition to scientific reactions, also led to social reactions. For example, strict governmental decrees and laws were enacted regarding the translation of Greek writings into Arabic, and Christians were excluded from administrative positions, particularly by Umar ibn Abdul Aziz. [29]

This movement gained further momentum during the Abbasid era, especially during the time of Ma'mun. With the influx of philosophical and theological questions, which had previously been less prevalent, and the ideas and thoughts of various nations into the Islamic world, along with the emergence of diverse theories and the subsequent turmoil in cultural and social conditions, Muslims sought to resolve these questions and doubts. A glance at some of the written and translated works of this period clearly indicates the growth of knowledge in various fields. The book "Al-Radd Ala Aristalis (Aristotle) fi al-Tawhid," authored by Hisham ibn Hakam [30], and the translation of some astronomical books from India by Abu Ishaq al-Farazi [31] are examples of such works. [32]

Although the foundations of some sects were established in the wake of this multiplicity of ideas and certain goals were set for them by the governments, this endeavour was not without benefit for the Islamic society. In addition to providing an opportunity for a detailed explanation of the teachings of the Ahl al-Bayt (peace be upon them), many doubts were also answered by the Imams and their knowledgeable companions. For instance, the Zanadiqa (a heretical sect) attempted to revive and propagate the ancient religions of Iran. Therefore, by translating some writings into Arabic, they spread some of the teachings of ancient Iranian religions, such as dualism and the Manichaean, Zoroastrian, and Mazdakite faiths, among the people. Ibn al-Muqaffa, a scribe in the Abbasid court, was one of the most prolific figures in this field. Al-Mahdi al-Abbasi, commenting on his role in spreading Zanadiqa's thought, said:

"I have not found any book on Zandaqa (heresy) except that its origin and roots trace back to Ibn al-Muqaffa." [33]

Masudi also writes:

"Abdullah ibn al-Muqaffa and others translated the books of Mani, Ibn Wisan, and Marcion (Zoroastrian priests) from Persian and Pahlavi into Arabic. Ibn Abi al-Awja, Hammad Ajrad, Yahya ibn Zayd, Mati ibn Iyas, and others wrote books in support of those books." [34]

This approach, along with a collection of narrations about the conversations between Imam al-Sadiq (peace be upon him) and some of these individuals, indicates the Imam's position and role in this movement.

1.3. Social Factors

Society consists of individuals who come together based on certain characteristics and factors, establishing relationships and interactions among themselves. Therefore, our understanding of social factors encompasses those that influence the relationships between members of society and extend beyond the specific outcomes of cultural and economic factors.

The following are the most important of these factors:

1.3.1. Expansion of Islamic Territories

A review of the expansion of Islamic territories reveals that during the Abbasid era, the extent of Islamic lands reached its peak. This vastness, coupled with the lack of political capacity to govern them, especially in remote areas, enabled Shi'ites – particularly the Banu Hashim – to migrate to distant cities to escape political repression and pursue other objectives, thereby spreading Shi'a intellectual works. Consequently, significant social bases were established for Shiites, where they could freely engage in their activities, sometimes even leading to the acquisition of political power. [35] For instance, figures like Lady Masumah (peace be upon her), Abdul Azim al-Hasani, and other migrants from the Ahl al-Bayt, the Barmaki family, [36] Ibrahim ibn Hashim al-Qumi, [37] and others migrated to cities like Qom, Ray, and others to the extent that some individuals from Qom, such as Hussain ibn Ashkib, migrated to even more distant regions like Kashmir to disseminate knowledge. [38]

Another example is a letter from Imam Askari (peace be upon him) to Ishaq ibn Ismail al-Naysaburi, which, after offering moral advice and valuable guidance—including the importance of divine guidance through the divine successors and the fact that the Imams of guidance (peace be upon them) are the gates of divine knowledge and possess obligatory rights—states:

"O Ishaq! You are my messenger to Ibrahim Abda, so that he may act upon what I have sent in a letter to Muhammad ibn Musa al-Naysaburi. And likewise, you and all those who live in your city are obliged to act upon the contents of that letter." [39]

This part of the letter clearly indicates the emergence of a suitable environment for the spread of knowledge in the eastern region of the vast Islamic land.

1.3.2. Population Dispersion

In light of the previous discussion, the Shi'a population, the number of scholars and students of knowledge in various regions increased, and the scope of Shi'a missionary activities as a religious power flourished and became more liberalized. In the shadow of this population dispersion, the active communication of scholars to acquire religious sciences and knowledge intensified, leading to their travels to regions such as Samarkand, Nishapur, Qom, Ahvaz, Fars, Kerman, Mazandaran, and Qazvin. As a result, the organisation of representation (wikalah) and its expansion in both financial and religious dimensions followed. [40]

1.3.3. Public Acceptance and Social Standing

Possessing social standing is a crucial factor in presenting behavioural models. In periods when the Ahl al-Bayt (peace be upon them) were not regarded highly by the general public due to certain previous issues, their conduct and behaviour were also not given much attention, nor were they used as suitable behavioural models. The manifestation of this reality can be observed in the extent to which they were consulted. For instance, during the time of Imam Sajjad (peace be upon him) and before, the transmission of narrations from the Imams was very limited, and no one approached them to seek hadiths, while seeking knowledge from other scholars was flourishing.

Towards the end of Imam Sajjad's (peace be upon him) era, this situation gradually changed. The famous poems of Farazdaq [41] in Mecca, and the behaviour of the people, clearly indicate the gradual increase in the Imam's significance in society. For example, the reciters and people of Medina would go to Mecca when Imam Sajjad (peace be upon him) would also go to perform rituals. [42] However, there were no questions asked of the Imam, nor was there any motivation to do so.

This trend completely reversed in the era of Imam Baqir (peace be upon him) and afterwards. There was extensive attention given to the Imamate in resolving issues, with people turning to the Imams and their Shi'a followers. In other words, a general approach contrary to the previous period emerged. Imam al-Sadiq (peace be upon him) says in this regard:

"The Shi'a, before the time of Abu Ja'far (Imam Baqir), did not know the rituals of their Hajj, nor what was lawful and unlawful for them... until Abu Ja'far came and explained to them their Hajj rituals and what was lawful and unlawful for them, to the extent that people became dependent on them after they had been dependent on others." [43]

To the extent that a significant portion of the questions posed by Muslims during the era of the two Sadiqs (peace be upon them) were asked during the Hajj pilgrimage. For example, Muhammad ibn Muslim asked approximately forty-six thousand questions from the two Sadiqs, a portion of which were during the Hajj season. [44]

This phenomenon also held true for the Shi'ites. The Islamic society's attention to the Shi'ites and their acceptance as an influential group—the Shi'a of Ja'far (peace be upon him)—was such that Imam al-Sadiq advised them to observe certain points, albeit cautiously, in this regard:

"O group of Shi'a who are attributed to us, be an adornment for us, not a source of shame and disgrace. What prevents you from being among people like Ali's companions (peace be upon him)? So that if one of his companions were among a tribe, he would be their imam, their muezzin, their trustee, and the protector of their wealth. Visit their sick, attend their funerals, and pray in their mosques. Do not let them surpass you in good deeds. By God, you are more deserving of it than they are." [45]

The words of Sharik, the judge of Kufa, about two of the Imam's companions—Muhammad ibn Muslim and Abu Kariba—after using the phrase "Jafarians, the Fatimids," clearly indicate this influence: "If there are men, let them be like you." [46]

Furthermore, the designation of the ninth and eleventh Imams (peace be upon them) as Ibn al-Ridha, which was originally a political title, demonstrates the manifestation of Imam Reza's (peace be upon him) personality and its impact on public opinion in later periods.

Qasim ibn Abd al-Rahman, a Zaydi, recounts his experience of an event in Baghdad:

"During my stay in Baghdad, one day I saw people crowding, coming and going, climbing to high places, and standing. I asked what was happening?! They said, "Ibn al-Ridha!" [47]

In this statement, in addition to the aforementioned reality, namely the manifestation of Imam Reza's (peace be upon him) personality, a picture is presented of the crowds of people in Baghdad eager to see the Imam, which clearly indicates his status among the people.

1.4. Economic Power

The foundation of certain movements and even their influence on historical elements depend on economic power. From this perspective, our understanding of economic factors refers to the flow of finances in various sectors and, in other words, the economic power of society.

Examples of utilising financial resources to halt and hinder cultural progress include: the defection of prominent figures like Talha and Zubayr and the ensuing Battle of Jamal; expenditures on the fabrication of false narrations; the disintegration of Imam Hassan's (peace be upon him) army and the withdrawal of commanders; the spread of moral corruption; and the prevalence of singers and immorality.

Furthermore, a reflection on the narrational sources reveals the extent to which the funds received by the organisation of representation (wikalah) were influential in promoting the school of the Ahl al-Bayt (peace be upon them).

For instance, these funds were utilized in at least four main areas:

- First, address the economic needs of the Imamate region, considering the existing sensitivities and the surveillance of the Imams.
- Second, meeting the economic needs of Shi'ites and needy Sayyids, and resolving financial disputes among Shi'ites,
- Third, providing stipends and gifts to Shi'ites, committed poets, and new converts to Islam for the dissemination of knowledge.
- Fourth, ensuring the livelihood of representatives and agents of the organisation of representation to carry out their assigned duties.

The impact of these factors on cultural and social progress clearly demonstrates why the Abbasid rulers sought to uncover and undermine this institution. In one instance, Imam al-Sadiq (peace be upon him) strongly confronted Dawud ibn Ali, the head of the Baghdad police and the killer of Ma'li ibn Khunis, one of the main figures responsible for the Imam's financial affairs and who played a role in the communication network between the Imam (peace be upon him) and the Shi'ites, saying, "O Dawud! Why did you kill my master and the guardian of my wealth and my family? By God, he is more honourable in the sight of God than you." [48]

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